

OFDM-based JCAS under Attack: The Dual Threat of Spoofing and Jamming in WLAN Sensing

Hasan Can Yildirim, *Member, IEEE*, Musa Furkan Keskin, *Member, IEEE*,
Henk Wymeersch, *Fellow, IEEE*, François Horlin, *Member, IEEE*

Abstract—This study reveals the vulnerabilities of Wireless Local Area Networks (WLAN) sensing, under the scope of joint communication and sensing (JCAS), focusing on target spoofing and deceptive jamming techniques. Utilizing orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM), we explore how adversaries can exploit WLAN’s sensing capabilities to inject false targets and disrupt normal operations. Unlike traditional methods that require sophisticated digital radio-frequency memory hardware, we demonstrate that much simpler software-defined radios can effectively serve as deceptive jammers in WLAN settings. Through comprehensive modeling and practical experiments, we show how deceptive jammers can manipulate the range-Doppler map (RDM) by altering signal integrity, thereby posing significant security threats to OFDM-based JCAS systems. Our findings comprehensively evaluate jammer impact on RDMs and propose several jamming strategies that vary in complexity and detectability.

Index Terms—JCAS, ISAC, WLAN sensing, target spoofing, deceptive jammer.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless local area network (WLAN) sensing [1] is a pioneering technology for joint communication and sensing (JCAS) [2], enabling detection, tracking, and interpretation of the environment through radio signals. By leveraging orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM), WLAN provides channel measurements for applications like indoor localization [3] where two devices, Alice and Bob, alternately function as transmitter and receiver in a half-duplex mode within a bistatic configuration, as shown in Fig. 1. To achieve this, the line-of-sight (LOS) between Alice and Bob is used as the timing reference, whereas the echoes from the targets, called surveillance signals, are received and processed by Bob. However, WLAN sensing, or more generally OFDM-based JCAS, is vulnerable to security threats. A potential jammer, empowered with extensive capabilities, can i) eavesdrop on sensing-related information and ii) transmit jamming signals that interfere with Bob’s reception, which can significantly distort the surveillance signal and the subsequent range-Doppler map (RDM). In particular, an adversary, referred to as Eve, can disrupt normal sensing operations by injecting artificial

Fig. 1. Jammer scenario topology with relevant line-of-sight (LOS) distances d_{ab} , d_{ea} , and d_{eb} , and LOS angles $\theta_0^{(a)}$, $\theta_0^{(b)}$, and θ_0 . Alice operates as a pulsed radar by continuously transmitting the same OFDM symbol of duration T_o , with a PRI of $T_s \gg T_o$.

targets, as in *target spoofing*, or alter the perception of real targets, as in *deceptive jamming*.

Historically, when attacking a radar system, the deceptive jammers need to estimate system operation parameters, reconstruct the waveforms, mimic real targets with propagation delays and Doppler shifts, and retransmit within the victim radar’s time frame. This typically requires digital radio-frequency memory (DRFM) hardware. However, the DRFM is very complex since it requires high-speed, high-fidelity sampling and storage of RF signals which necessitates advanced analog-to-digital converters, large memory capacity, and fast data processing units. Hence, DRFMs are not feasible for civil applications. However, WLAN sensing uses standardized OFDM symbols, which allows for bypassing DRFM requirements by employing software-defined radios (SDRs) as deceptive jammers. This study investigates the design and impact of deceptive jammers on WLAN sensing, uncovering vulnerabilities in current technologies and potential security threats in future OFDM-based JCAS systems.

Various attacks that can disrupt communication or sensing have been investigated in the literature. Comprehensive surveys are provided in [4], [5] which investigate various jamming attacks and anti-jamming techniques that target wireless networks using OFDM waveforms. In [6], a survey on the physical layer security aspects of OFDM signals is conducted. Vulnerabilities in Wi-Fi frame detection, synchronization, and channel estimation are exploited in [7] to dramatically reduce the communication throughput. Different spoofing attacks, their impacts, and success rates have been thoroughly investigated in [8], leading to the development of a layered model to

Hasan Can Yildirim and François Horlin are with the Wireless Communications Group, Université Libre de Bruxelles, Belgium. Musa Furkan Keskin and Henk Wymeersch are with the Department of Electrical Engineering, Chalmers University of Technology, Sweden.

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classify spoofing attacks based on deployment architectures, take-over strategies, control strategies, and applications. A new type of attack, jamming with beamforming, is studied in [9] which exploits the explicit feedback mechanism used in 802.11ac networks. Authors in [10] have shown that by using targeted Wi-Fi geolocation spoofing, a device-to-identity linking attack can be established. Similarly, attacks on public WLAN-based positioning systems have been investigated in [11] which implies that positioning information can also be spoofed with an accurate model of the underlying scenario. In [12], the authors have investigated methods to identify location spoofing devices in wireless networks, especially when line-of-sight is not present.

Since 5G also employs OFDM waveform, similar attacks have also been studied. In [13], [14], various surveys are conducted that investigate the vulnerabilities of 5G networks in the physical layer. Smart jamming attacks, such as jamming, spoofing, and sniffing attacks are investigated. It is shown that various potential loopholes exist in 5G networks, from exploiting the time-frequency synchronization to useful signal nullification through beamforming. The authors in [10] have investigated the physical layer security aspects of OFDM waveforms. Moreover, the same principles used in jamming attacks are shown to be useful for privacy enhancement. In [15], a delay-angle information spoofing strategy is used for location-privacy enhancement. By shifting the location-relevant delays and angles at the transmitter, a potential eavesdropper is obfuscated by a physical location that is distinct from the true one. Similarly, a fake path injection scheme has been proposed in [16] to preserve location privacy, leveraging geometrically feasible fake paths that are indistinguishable from true paths to illegitimate devices, thereby hindering their localization abilities.

In the meantime, different countermeasures against jamming attacks have been proposed in the literature. To counteract a jammer that mimics authorized signals that disrupt communication, a novel method to securely precode the OFDM system has been proposed in [17]. Techniques to prevent unauthorized receivers from accurately estimating the range and Doppler of a wireless emitter using OFDM have also been investigated in [18]. A novel design of diverse time-frequency modulation which employs a modulated metasurface is proposed in [19], where each element is independently time-modulated to create specific false targets in the radar's high-resolution range profile. The effectiveness of randomly generated OFDM waveforms in synthetic aperture radar imaging under deceptive jamming conditions has also been explored in [20]. In [21], a physical layer authentication method based on angle-of-arrival information is developed to eliminate impersonating devices such as jammers. In [22]–[24] various machine/deep learning methods are used to detect 5G signal jammers, such as supervised and unsupervised learning on signal spectrograms, autoencoder based on loose observations of signals on air, with convolutional neural networks and support vector machines. Based on the findings of the authors, it can be stated that there is not a single method that can be used to detect jamming signals in all types of conditions and scenarios.

In our previous work [25], we explored the vulnerabilities

of WLAN Sensing within JCAS. We provided an initial mathematical framework with simplified scenario-related assumptions to understand how such jamming could introduce artificial targets, thereby misleading the radar receiver. The study primarily emphasized the feasibility of using OFDM waveforms in deceptive jamming scenarios and provided experimental validation of these vulnerabilities.

Building on this foundation, this study greatly expands the scope by providing a comprehensive model for spoofing and jamming, a sophisticated framework for jamming strategies, and advanced experimental validations. While giving extensive capabilities to the jammer, we maintain the WLAN sensing framework in its current form and focus on RDM-based sensing. This methodology is intended to reveal the vulnerabilities inherent in WLAN sensing systems, and more broadly, in all OFDM-based JCAS systems, when subjected to target spoofing and deceptive jamming. Our primary contributions are summarized as follows:

- **Spoofing and Jamming Framework:** We introduce a detailed mathematical framework for target spoofing and deceptive jamming in WLAN sensing systems. We begin with a basic single-antenna, single-target jamming model that highlights the intricacies of signal generation and the interaction between the jamming and legitimate sensing signals. This foundational model is then expanded to include more sophisticated scenarios involving multiple antennas and advanced target mimicry techniques. We show that these enhancements allow the jammer to more effectively disrupt the sensing process, significantly increasing the impact of the attack as well as the jammer's complexity.
- **Evaluation of Strategies and Their Implications:** We systematically evaluate various jamming strategies, considering their complexity, effectiveness, and detectability. Our analysis covers both simple jamming techniques and more advanced methods that exploit vulnerabilities in OFDM-based JCAS systems. We demonstrate how these strategies can distort RDMs, thereby compromising the integrity of the sensing process and posing significant security threats.
- **Experimental Validation with SDR Platforms:** To validate our theoretical findings, we implement the proposed jamming strategies using SDR platforms. Our experiments confirm the feasibility of executing sophisticated jamming attacks with relatively simple and accessible hardware, highlighting the real-world applicability of our approach and the pressing need for enhanced security measures in WLAN sensing systems.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. WLAN sensing framework, the scenario, system model, and radar processing are described in Section II. The basic jammer functionalities, such as signal generation, jammer channel, and the jammed RDM are modeled in Section III. Based on these analyses, various advanced jamming strategies and their complexity as well as effectiveness are discussed in Section IV. Numerical analyses are provided in Section V, which are experimentally validated in Section VI. Finally, the

conclusion is drawn in Section VII

Notation: Matrices and vectors are given by bold characters, \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{x} , respectively, whereas $x[n]$ corresponds to the n th entry in \mathbf{x} . The Hadamard product \odot and division \oslash correspond to the element-wise multiplication and division between matrices or vectors of the same size, respectively. The forward and inverse Fourier transform matrices of size N are defined as \mathbf{F}_N and \mathbf{F}_N^H , respectively, where \mathbf{F}_N^H is the Hermitian transpose of \mathbf{F}_N . The Dirichlet function is defined as $D_N(x, y) = \exp(j\pi \frac{N-1}{N}(x-y)) \sin(\pi(x-y)) / \sin(\pi(y-y)/N)$ for $x \neq y$ and $D_N(x, x) = N$. Finally, the phase of a cisoid is obtained as $\angle(e^{-jX}) = -X$.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

In this section, we describe the high-level jammer scenario. Then, we detail the sensing framework and signal processing chain under nominal operating conditions (i.e., without a jammer). Finally, we identify the main vulnerabilities in WLAN sensing.

A. Scenario Description

The scenario, consisting of three stationary devices, Alice, Bob, and Eve, and a mobile target, is shown in Fig. 1. Alice and Bob are involved in the legitimate WLAN Sensing, while Eve acts as the jammer. Table I details the operating modes of the devices during different stages of the process.

1) *WLAN Sensing:* Alice and Bob operate in a half-duplex mode and alternately function as the transmitter (Tx) or the receiver (Rx). They use OFDM to perform channel measurements within a bistatic configuration. To do so, an initial *negotiation* stage takes place, where Alice and Bob establish an agreement on the sensing parameters and localize each other. During this stage, they exchange their respective roles as Tx and Rx. Subsequently, a radar *measurement* instance starts. During this stage, Alice emits the sensing signals, which Bob receives and processes for sensing purposes. The signal captured by Bob is referred to as the surveillance signal, and it is utilized for sensing. Although many sensing methods exist (spectrogram, super-resolution, etc.), we assume that Bob implements the most widely used method: range/Doppler processing yielding an RDM.

2) *Jamming:* While WLAN sensing is taking place, an adversarial device, Eve, intervenes with the WLAN sensing procedure. It attacks by transmitting jamming signals, which can introduce artificial targets to Bob, and potentially invalidate the surveillance signal perceived by Bob. To achieve these, Eve has to operate in a dual capacity: i) as a receiver during sensing negotiation between Alice and Bob to *eavesdrop* on the sensing parameters, and to potentially deduce other metrics related to the topology, and ii) as a transmitter during a sensing measurement to emit *spoofing and jamming* signals targeting Bob.

B. WLAN Sensing – Detailed Operation

In this section, we detail the WLAN sensing framework, based on [1], [26]. For the envisioned use cases, we refer to

TABLE I
EACH DEVICE'S ROLE DURING A GIVEN STAGE.

WLAN Sensing	Negotiation		Measurement
Alice	Tx	Rx	Tx
Bob	Rx	Tx	Rx
<i>Sensing Attack</i>	Eavesdropping		Jamming
Eve	Rx	Rx	Tx

[3]. We describe the sensing stages, the transmitted sensing signals, the surveillance channel, and finally the received-side signal processing chain.

1) *Stages of WLAN Sensing:* The WLAN sensing uses the synchronization protocols initially implemented to enable multi-user multi-input multi-output in the 802.11ac amendment [27]. In essence, this protocol allows a Tx to trigger channel sounding with explicit feedback from an Rx. To do so, the Tx (Alice) emits two packets called null data packet announcement (NDPA) and null data packet (NDP), containing training fields for channel estimation. Then, Rx (Bob) estimates the channel transfer function (CTF) from NDPA/NDP. Depending on the configuration, Bob can either send the estimated CTF back to Alice, or it can compute the RDM itself. The WLAN sensing framework is composed of five stages, summarized as follows:

- 1) *Sensing session setup* is the first level of agreement, where Alice discovers potential responders like Bob. During this stage, Alice and Bob estimate the distance between each other through round-trip time as explained in Appendix C, where we assume that LOS is present and resolvable.
- 2) *Sensing measurement setup* is where Alice and Bob agree on sensing parameters (such as bandwidth, number of antennas, carrier frequency, pulse repetition interval, and subcarrier grouping) with over-the-air transmission. Hence, any device can eavesdrop on the transmitted signals to deduce the sensing parameters agreed upon by Alice and Bob.
- 3) *Sensing measurement instance* is the stage where the sensing takes place, i.e., Alice emits NDPA/NDP, and Bob estimates the CTFs. *WLAN sensing uses a pulsed-OFDM radar scheme*, where successive NDPA/NDP transmissions are separated by a fixed pulse repetition interval. Since the number of samples in NDPA/NDP is defined by the standard, Bob knows how many samples it should collect before waiting for the next OFDM pulse. When the jammer framework is introduced, this will play a crucial role.
- 4) *Sensing measurement and session termination* are the two stages where Alice and Bob release their resources dedicated to sensing.

For ease of reference, we refer to the combination of the sensing session setup and sensing measurement setup as sensing negotiation.

In the remainder of this section, the sensing system model and radar processing will be provided, where Alice and Bob act as the Tx and Rx, respectively. Therefore, we assume that the sensing negotiation already took place.

2) *Transmitted Signal:* The OFDM parameters are defined as follows: f_c is the carrier frequency, Q is the number of

subcarriers, Q_{cp} is the cyclic prefix (CP) length, M is the number of OFDM symbols, q and m represent the subcarrier and slow-time indices, respectively, T , T_o and T_s correspond to the sampling interval, the duration of an OFDM symbol including the CP, and the pulse repetition interval (PRI) which is an integer multiple of T_o , respectively and $T_s \gg T_o$, and $\Delta_f = 1/(QT)$ is the subcarrier spacing. The signal transmitted by Alice in the frequency domain is then defined as $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{R}^{Q \times M}$, comprising standardized BPSK¹ symbols whose M columns are identical. In the time domain, the signal structure resembles a pulsed radar where the OFDM symbols are separated by T_s seconds as shown on Fig. 1².

3) *Surveillance Channel*: Let us define the steering vectors for the propagation delay as follows

$$\mathbf{d}(\tau) = [1 e^{-j2\pi\tau\Delta_f} \dots e^{-j2\pi\tau(Q-1)\Delta_f}]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{Q \times 1}, \quad (1)$$

where τ_p is the bi-static propagation delay. Similarly, the steering vector for the Doppler frequency shift is defined as

$$\mathbf{b}(f) = [1 e^{-j2\pi f T_s} \dots e^{-j2\pi f (M-1)T_s}]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}, \quad (2)$$

where f is the Doppler frequency. The surveillance channel between Alice and Bob is defined in the frequency domain as

$$\mathbf{H} = \sum_{p=0}^P \alpha_p \mathbf{d}(\tau_p) \mathbf{b}^H(f_p), \in \mathbb{C}^{Q \times M}. \quad (3)$$

Here, the path index $p = 0$ models the LOS with complex amplitude $\alpha_0 = a_0 e^{-j2\pi\tau_0 f_c}$, where a_0 represents path loss. The remaining indices model the target reflection, each with a complex amplitude α_p , a bi-static propagation delay τ_p , and a bi-static Doppler frequency shift f_p . The propagation delays are assumed to be sorted in decreasing order, i.e., $\tau_0 < \tau_1 < \dots < \tau_P$. Hence $\Delta_\tau = \tau_P - \tau_0$ represents the delay spread of the channel.

4) *Receiver Signal Processing Stage 1 – Time-Frequency Synchronization*: In a bistatic geometry, the receiver, Bob, needs time and frequency synchronization [1], [28]. To do so, Bob uses an auto-correlation algorithm³ to estimate the time of arrival based on the detection of amplitude peaks. Hence, assuming that LOS is present and dominant, the signal propagated through it will be used for joint time-frequency synchronization. We define the strongest peak at the output of the lag-1 auto-correlation [29], [30] without losing any generality as follows

$$\Xi[n_0] = |\alpha_0|^2 e^{-j2\pi\eta T_s} + z_0, \quad (4)$$

where z_0 is the noise sample obtained after correlation, and $n_0 = (\tau_0 + \delta_t)/T$ is the sample index of the LOS signal at the correlator's output with δ_t modeling the clock offset (see

Appendix A for derivations)⁴. Since the phase of the peak is associated with the CFO, η , between Bob and Alice, Bob can detect the peak at $k = n_0$ for time synchronization⁵ and use its phase for frequency synchronization, correcting the CFO via $\hat{\eta} = \angle \Xi[n_0]/(2\pi T_s)$. This synchronization step will be crucial when the jamming framework is introduced.

Following the joint time and frequency synchronization, Bob performs the standard OFDM demodulation (removal of CP and FFT over each symbol), leading to the following received signal in the frequency domain:

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{H}_0 \odot \mathbf{S} + \mathbf{Z}, \quad (5)$$

where the entries in $\mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{C}^{Q \times M}$ correspond to the noise samples in the frequency domain with zero mean and σ^2 variance. Here, the CTF perceived by Bob \mathbf{H}_0 is defined as

$$\mathbf{H}_0 = \sum_{p=0}^P \alpha_p \mathbf{d}(\tau_p - \tau_0) \mathbf{b}^H(f_p). \quad (6)$$

Here, we assume no time and frequency synchronization errors. Due to prior time synchronization, the propagation delays τ_p are now *relative* to the direct path τ_0 propagation delay. This is indicated by the zero-index on \mathbf{H}_0 . Meanwhile, the CFO is compensated without errors; hence, the corresponding term does not appear on the estimated CTF.

5) *Receiver Signal Processing Stage 2 – Radar Processing*: The CTF estimated by Bob is defined as follows

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}_0 = \mathbf{R} \oslash \mathbf{S} = \mathbf{H}_0 + \mathbf{Z} \oslash \mathbf{S}.$$

Since the training fields, \mathbf{S} , are composed of BPSK symbols, the CTF estimation does not affect the noise variance, hence, no enhancement in the noise energy. The RDM, $\hat{\mathbf{Y}} \in \mathbb{C}^{Q \times M}$, is obtained through inverse discrete Fourier transforms (IDFT) over q and discrete Fourier transforms over m (DFT) as follows

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}} = \mathbf{F}_Q \hat{\mathbf{H}}_0 \mathbf{F}_M^H, \in \mathbb{C}^{Q \times M}. \quad (7)$$

where matrix $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}$ contains $P + 1$ peaks. The peak at zero-range/zero-Doppler corresponds to the direct path used as the reference, while the remaining P peaks correspond to the target echoes. Once an RDM is obtained, a constant false-alarm rate (CFAR) detector separates the target echo peaks from noise peaks [28]. Finally, we define the RDM processing operator $\hat{\mathbf{Y}} = \Sigma(\hat{\mathbf{H}})$ which encapsulates the range IDFT and Doppler DFTs as described in (7).

C. Vulnerabilities

For future reference, we underline the following facts since they will play a crucial role in jamming. First of all, the transmitted signals, \mathbf{S} , are standardized and known. This makes the target spoofing and deceptive jamming with SDRs much easier since signal reconstruction can be bypassed. Secondly, Bob synchronizes to the peak with the largest amplitude at the

¹Wi-Fi standardization uses only BPSK symbols for training fields.

²In reality, a single frame consists of many OFDM symbols in different fields, each serving various purposes as detailed in Section VI. The last field in a given NDP/NPA/NDP is known as the high-efficiency long training field (HE-LTF) for 802.11ax. This field is mainly used for fine synchronization, channel estimation, and sensing. We simplify the transmission scheme as if the entire frame consists of only HE-LTFs.

³Auto-correlation, used for coarse synchronization, has unique advantages against multipath. Later, cross-correlation is also used for fine synchronization.

⁴In reality, a single pulse transmission from Alice consists of many OFDM symbols composing a Wi-Fi frame. Bob uses successively received legacy short and long training fields (L-STFs and L-LTFs) for synchronization. However, these fields are separated by T_o seconds. Since we have simplified the signal structure used for sensing, the phase in Equation 4 evolves with T_s which should be replaced by T_o to be fully standard compliant in a real-life setting.

⁵This approach allows the receiver to synchronize with the time-of-arrival, but neither δ_t nor τ_0 can directly be estimated from n_0 .

output of its correlator. This allows Eve to potentially deceive Bob in different ways.

III. DECEPTIVE JAMMER FRAMEWORK

The jammer, Eve, has two main goals. The first one is to *inject artificial targets* into Bob, as in target spoofing. The second goal is to *invalidate the surveillance signal* and the true target echoes that it contains, as in deceptive jamming. To achieve these goals, we assume that Eve knows the sensing parameters⁶ ($Q, Q_{cp}, M, T, f_c, T_s$) established between Alice and Bob during the sensing negotiation. Moreover, the channel parameters for each bistatic geometry (Alice-Bob, Alice-Eve, and Eve-Bob) are assumed to be different.

A. Time Alignment between the Surveillance and Jamming Signals at Bob

Jamming takes place during a sensing measurement where Alice is transmitting sensing signals for Bob to receive. Due to the nature of the OFDM waveform, the time alignment between these two signals at Bob yields different consequences. The corresponding cases are shown in Fig. 2 and summarized as follows.

- *Case 1: Eve's signal arrives earlier than Alice's:* There is no alignment between the two signals⁷. Hence, Bob synchronizes with Eve's signal, collects a predetermined amount of samples, and waits for the next OFDM symbol while completely omitting Alice's signal.
- *Case 2: Alice's and Eve's signals are partially aligned:* Bob will detect two peaks at the correlator output and synchronize with the one having the largest amplitude [29]. Whether Eve's signal arrives earlier (2a) or later (2b) has different consequences which are detailed in Section III-B3.
- *Case 3: Eve's signal arrives later than Alice's:* Bob will only sample Alice's signals, causing jamming to fail.

Since the 802.11 standard does not dictate specific receiver design, hardware vendors have the flexibility to determine Bob's timing window for signal reception. If Bob has a reliable RTT-based distance estimation and is configured to operate with a very narrow timing window, then the scenario described in Case 1 would likely be invalid. In such a configuration, Bob would only be vulnerable against Case 2.

B. Jammer Operation

The mathematical models are only derived for Case 2, which is the most general one. Due to the introduction of the jamming signal, there will be four different sets of channel parameters and CFOs. For easy reference, these are summarized in Table II. Even though the number of targets can potentially be equal (i.e., $P = L$), their channel parameters will not be, i.e., amplitudes $\alpha_p \neq \alpha_l^{(b)}$, propagation delays $\tau_p \neq \tau_l^{(b)}$, and Doppler frequencies $f_p \neq f_l^{(b)}$ for $\forall p, l$.

⁶Either by eavesdropping during sensing negotiation or sensing measurement. The former is more straightforward since it only involves demodulating the appropriate fields in the preamble. The latter is more complicated since it requires the estimation of all the parameters directly from samples.

⁷The tail of Eve's signal may align with the CP of Alice's signal. In this case, the surveillance channel may be observed at very large distances, e.g., hundreds of meters, and the peaks will be ignored by Bob.

Fig. 2. Different signal alignment cases during jamming. Green and red boxes correspond to Alice and Eve signals, respectively, while $\Delta\tau$ and T_o are the delay spread and OFDM symbol duration, respectively.

Parameter\Channel	A-B	B-E	E
Number of targets	P	L	1
Path index	p	l	-
Path gain	α_p	$\alpha_l^{(b)}$	$\bar{\alpha}$
Path delay	τ_p	$\tau_l^{(b)}$	$\bar{\tau}$
Path Doppler frequency	f_p	$f_l^{(b)}$	\bar{f}
Path angles	θ_p	$\theta_l^{(b)}$	-
CFO	η	$\eta^{(b)}$	$\bar{\eta}$

TABLE II

FROM LEFT TO RIGHT, THE COLUMNS CORRESPOND TO THE ALICE-BOB (A-B) AND BOB-EVE (B-E) PAIRS, WHILE THE LAST COLUMN CORRESPONDS TO THE PARAMETERS OF THE ARTIFICIAL TARGET GENERATED BY EVE (E).

1) *Jamming Transmitter:* Eve generates the deceptive signal by reversing the radar processing stages and exploiting the delay-frequency and time-Doppler dualities in [31]. First, the artificial CTF generated by Eve is defined as

$$\bar{\mathbf{H}} = \mathbf{1} + \bar{\alpha} \mathbf{d}(\bar{\tau}) \mathbf{b}^H(\bar{f}), \in \mathbb{C}^{Q \times M}, \quad (8)$$

Here, $\mathbf{1} \in \mathbb{R}^{Q \times M}$ is a matrix of ones which allows us to generate a reference peak at zero-range/zero-Doppler. With the second term, a single artificial and mobile target is generated with amplitude $\bar{\alpha}$, propagation delay $\bar{\tau} > 0, \bar{\tau} \in \mathbb{R}$, and Doppler frequency $\bar{f} \in \mathbb{R}$.

Then, after modulating each subcarrier with $\bar{\mathbf{H}}$ and \mathbf{S} , the symbols that will be transmitted are defined as $\bar{\mathbf{H}} \odot \mathbf{S}, \in \mathbb{C}^{Q \times M}$.

Finally, these modulated OFDM symbols can now be transmitted in the time domain by computing the IDFT over q and adding the CP.

2) *Jamming Channel:* During the sensing measurement instance, Eve transmits the jamming signals through the channel between itself and Bob. We denote the corresponding frequency-domain channel by

$$\mathbf{B} = \sum_{l=0}^L \alpha_l^{(b)} \mathbf{d}(\tau_l^{(b)}) \mathbf{b}^H(f_l^{(b)}) \in \mathbb{C}^{Q \times M}. \quad (9)$$

Here, $\alpha_l^{(b)}$, $\tau_l^{(b)}$, and $f_l^{(b)}$ correspond to the amplitude, propagation delay, and Doppler frequency of the l th path between Eve and Bob. Meanwhile, $l = 0$ refers to the LOS, and since the device is assumed to be stationary, $f_0^{(b)} = 0$.

3) *Receiver Signal Processing Stage 1 – Time-Frequency Synchronization:* If a jammer is present, Bob can be forced to synchronize with the jammer signal. The only requirement is that the signal transmitted by Eve, and propagated through the LOS with Bob (Eve-LOS), should have 3 dB or more power at Bob than the one transmitted by Alice, and propagated through the corresponding LOS (Alice-LOS) [29].

As described in Section II-B4, Bob computes the lag-1 auto-correlation over the received samples. In this case, there

are two strict peaks at the following indices: $k = n_0$ and $k = n_0^{(b)}$ where $n_0^{(b)} = (\tau_0^{(b)} + \bar{\delta}_t)/T$ represents the time of arrival of Eve-LOS, with $\bar{\delta}_t$ being the clock offset. Similar to the definition of $\Xi[n_0]$ in (4), $\Xi[n_0^{(b)}]$ can be defined as

$$\Xi[n_0^{(b)}] = |\alpha_0^{(b)}|^2 e^{-j2\pi\eta^{(b)}T_s} + z_0, \quad (10)$$

where $\eta^{(b)}$ refers to the CFO between Eve and Bob. Since Bob synchronizes to the peak with the largest magnitude at the output of the correlator, and if we assume that $20 \log_{10}(|\alpha_0^{(b)}|) - 20 \log_{10}(|\alpha_0|) > 3\text{dB}$ (whether because $d_{eb} < d_{ab}$ or because Eve's transmit power is adjusted accordingly), Bob will time and frequency synchronize to Eve's jamming signal. This forced synchronization comes with different consequences.

- *Time synchronization implication:* If $n_0^{(b)} < n_0$, i.e., the jamming signal arrives *earlier* than the surveillance signal, Bob will be time synchronized with an earlier clock corresponding to the Case 2a. Hence, the targets on the surveillance RDM will be range-shifted⁸. On the other hand, if $n_0^{(b)} > n_0$ the jammer signal arrives *later* than the legitimate signal. If in addition $n_0^{(b)} - n_0 > Q_{cp}$ and $T_o = T_s$, the surveillance signal will be sampled beyond its CP, destroying its subcarrier orthogonality. These two cases have been studied in our earlier publication [25].
- *Frequency synchronization implication:* Bob will synchronize to the CFO of Eve, i.e., $\eta^{(b)}$. Hence, assuming the CFO is estimated without any errors, and if $\eta - \eta^{(b)}$ is significantly large⁹, the subcarrier orthogonality of the surveillance signal will be completely lost, turning it into interference regardless of the time alignment between the two signals. Hence, Bob will not be able to observe the surveillance channel at all.

In summary, if Bob can be forced to synchronize with Eve, Alice's surveillance signal will experience inter-carrier interference (ICI), mainly due to the CFO, but potentially due to sampling beyond the CP. Regardless, the surveillance RDM will be corrupted. Moreover, the CFO will shift the surveillance RDM along the speed dimension since it has the same effect as the Doppler frequency shift.

Following the time-frequency synchronization, Bob perceives the channel between Eve and itself as follows

$$\mathbf{B}_0 = \sum_{l=0}^L \alpha_l^{(b)} \mathbf{d}(\tau_l^{(b)} - \tau_0^{(b)}) \mathbf{b}^H(f_l^{(b)}), \in \mathbb{C}^{Q \times M} \quad (11)$$

where the delays are modeled relative to the direct path.

4) *Receiver Signal Processing Stage 2 – Radar Processing:* Assuming that Bob is force-synchronized with Eve, and demodulates the OFDM symbols, the estimated CTF takes the following form

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}_j = \underbrace{\mathbf{B}_0 \odot \bar{\mathbf{H}}}_{=\mathbf{G}_1} + \underbrace{\mathbf{H}' \odot \mathbf{C}}_{=\mathbf{G}_2} + \mathbf{Z}. \quad (12)$$

Here, $\bar{\mathbf{H}}$ is the artificial CTF, introduced in (8), \mathbf{B}_0 corresponds to the physical channel between Eve and Bob, \mathbf{H}' is the

desynchronized surveillance channel, and \mathbf{C} is the ICI. They are now described in detail. Hence, the first Hadamard product yields

$$\mathbf{G}_1 = \mathbf{B}_0 \odot \bar{\mathbf{H}} = \mathbf{B}_0 + \sum_{l=0}^L \alpha_l^{(b)} \bar{\alpha} \mathbf{d}(\tau_l^{(b)} - \tau_0^{(b)} + \bar{\tau}) \mathbf{b}^H(f_l^{(b)} + \bar{f}). \quad (13)$$

Compared to the channel \mathbf{H}_0 observed in (6), there are different types of targets observed in \mathbf{G}_1 . The first term corresponds to the channel between Eve and Bob \mathbf{B}_0 and is present due to the reference peak in the artificial RDM. The second term with $l = 0$ corresponds to the artificial target injected on delay/Doppler cell $(\bar{\tau}, \bar{f})$ when $l = 0$. The remaining L terms on delay/Doppler cells $(\tau_l^{(b)} + \bar{\tau}, f_l^{(b)} + \bar{f})$ are the real targets affected by the presence of the artificial target.

The desynchronized surveillance channel is

$$\mathbf{H}' = \sum_{p=0}^P \alpha_p \mathbf{d}(\tau_p - \tau') \mathbf{b}^H(f_k^{(a)} + \eta_w), \quad (14)$$

where the delays are now relative to $\tau' = \tau_0^{(b)} + \bar{\delta}_t$ due to the time synchronization and $\eta_w = \eta - \eta^{(b)}$ is the combined CFO. Consequently, the desynchronized surveillance channel \mathbf{H}' contains the same $P + 1$ peaks as \mathbf{H}_0 but these peaks are shifted in delay by τ' and in Doppler by η_w .

Finally, the ICI, present due to the forced time and frequency synchronization, is modeled with $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{P}\mathbf{S}\mathbf{A}$, [32] where the entries in $\mathbf{P} \in \mathbb{C}^{Q \times Q}$ are defined as

$$P[q, \bar{q}] = \frac{1 - e^{j2\pi(\frac{q-\bar{q}}{Q} - \eta_w T)Q}}{1 - e^{j2\pi(\frac{q-\bar{q}}{Q} - \eta_w T)}} \quad (15)$$

and the entries of the diagonal matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times M}$ are given as $\Lambda[m, m] = e^{-j2\pi\eta_w m T_s}$. For later reference, we define the second Hadamard product as $\mathbf{G}_2 = \mathbf{H}' \odot \mathbf{C}$. Here, \mathbf{C} mixes the subcarriers and greatly affects the detectability of real target peaks.

The jammed and corrupted RDM is obtained by range/Doppler processing $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_j$ as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{Y}}_j &= \mathbf{F}_Q \hat{\mathbf{H}}_j \mathbf{F}_M^H \\ &= \underbrace{\mathbf{F}_Q \mathbf{G}_1 \mathbf{F}_M^H}_{=\mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{G}_1}} + \underbrace{\mathbf{F}_Q \mathbf{G}_2 \mathbf{F}_M^H}_{=\mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{G}_2}} + \underbrace{\mathbf{F}_Q \mathbf{Z} \mathbf{F}_M^H}_{=\mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{Z}}} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Remark 1. The model in (16) can be generalized for the different time alignment cases from Fig. 2:

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}}_j = \begin{cases} \mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{G}_1} + \mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{Z}} & \text{Case 1} \\ \mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{G}_1} + \mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{G}_2} + \mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{Z}} & \text{Case 2} \\ \hat{\mathbf{Y}} + \mathbf{Z} & \text{Case 3.} \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

If the time alignment corresponds to the first case, then only the first Hadamard product remains in (16) since Alice's signal falls completely outside of the sampling window. The second case corresponds to the model provided in (16). Finally, the third case corresponds to the model provided in (7) where the surveillance channel is estimated as it is. Since Eve's jamming signals are not present at all, the jamming fails.

C. Achieving the Jammer Goals

From (16), the RDM comprises two terms, given by the two Hadamard products, and they correspond to Eve's goals.

⁸In case target echoes arrive later than $n_0^{(b)}$, there will be also intersymbol interference. However, considering the minimum duration of the CP (which is $0.8\mu\text{s}$), the targets should be beyond 120 meters to satisfy the given condition. Hence, we omit this interference term.

⁹Usually above $B/2Q$ is sufficient.

Fig. 3. Different jamming strategies to achieve Eve's goals.

1) *Injecting artificial targets*: This goal is achieved by the first Hadamard product, \mathbf{Y}_{G_1} , which combines the RDM between Eve and Bob ($\mathbf{Y}_{B_0} = \mathbf{F}_Q \mathbf{B}_0 \mathbf{F}_M^H$) with the artificially generated RDM ($\mathbf{Y}_{\bar{H}} = \mathbf{F}_Q \bar{\mathbf{H}} \mathbf{F}_M^H$). Here, \mathbf{Y}_{B_0} includes a reference peak at zero-range/zero-Doppler and physical targets at various range-Doppler cells, while $\mathbf{Y}_{\bar{H}}$ includes an artificial mobile target and a reference peak. This product results in weighted, and range/Doppler-shifted copies of $\mathbf{Y}_{\bar{H}}$ according to the peaks in \mathbf{Y}_{B_0} , with its reference peak serving as the baseline.

Limitations: The main drawback of injecting artificial targets is that each peak in \mathbf{Y}_{B_0} adds an extra copy of $\mathbf{Y}_{\bar{H}}$, potentially overcrowding the RDM. Although beneficial for Eve, this could alert Bob to an anomaly.

2) *Invalidating the surveillance RDM*: The second goal uses the Hadamard product \mathbf{Y}_{G_2} , which reflects the interaction between the desynchronized surveillance channel \mathbf{H}' and the ICI effects, \mathbf{C} . Without CFO and ICI, the surveillance channel remains observable as $\mathbf{Y}_{H'} = \mathbf{F}_Q \mathbf{H}' \mathbf{F}_M^H$. However, the ICI matrix \mathbf{C} spreads the energy across the range dimension after the range IDFT. Then, the Doppler DFT focuses this energy along a single Doppler cell relative to CFO, causing a so-called ridge [33]. Hence, each real target peak in $\mathbf{Y}_{H'}$ will be replaced by range/Doppler shifted copies of this ridge.

Limitations: The first limitation is that Bob can detect the ridges, which are known indicators of OFDM-based radar interference, and can respond effectively when detected. The second limitation is that Eve may unintentionally sabotage its artificial targets if they are aligned with the ridges.

IV. ADVANCED JAMMING STRATEGIES: A QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

More advanced jamming strategies and their combinations are provided and discussed in this section, as visualized in Fig. 3. First, artificial target injection strategies will be discussed, where the options are either overcrowding (A1) or selective target injection (A2). Both of these strategies can be further enhanced with advanced target mimicry (A3). Second, we will discuss methods to invalidate the surveillance signal by preceding jamming signal (B1) or by forced synchronization (B2). Finally, we will qualitatively rate these strategies based on their simplicity/complexity and various effects on Bob.

A. Injecting Artificial Targets

1) *Overcrowding*: This is a type of target spoofing in which many targets are introduced to Bob. These targets include artificial ones transmitted by Eve, real targets located between Eve and Bob, and combinations of both. However, since real

targets are also involved, Eve cannot fully control which range/Doppler cells these targets will occupy.

If Eve desires to overcrowd Bob's CFAR output, then the first Hadamard product in (16) should remain as it is, since it introduces $2(L+1)$ targets. The artificial target will appear at its intended RDM cell, while the real targets will be range/Doppler shifted according to the artificial target's parameters.

2) *Selective Target Injection*: This is a type of target spoofing in which Eve desires complete control of the targets introduced to Bob.

If Eve desires to have only the artificial target at Bob's CFAR output, then only the LOS path should be exploited. This can be achieved by equipping Eve with multiple antennas. In that case, Eve can estimate the angles $\hat{\theta}_0^{(a)}$, $\hat{\theta}_0^{(b)}$, and $\hat{\theta}_0$ shown in Fig. 1 during the sensing negotiation phase by using subspace-based methods, such as MUSIC [34] or ESPRIT [35]. Then, Eve can construct a precoder that steers a beam towards the LOS path to Bob $\hat{\theta}_0^{(b)}$ and nulls toward $\hat{\theta}_0^{(a)}$ and $\hat{\theta}_0$, as described in Appendix B. Once the radiation pattern is adjusted, only the first term in (11) will remain, meaning that \mathbf{Y}_{B_0} will contain only the peak at zero-range/Zero-Doppler. Hence, $\mathbf{Y}_{\bar{H}}$ will have a single copy at Bob.

3) *Advanced Target Mimicry*: Bob can be equipped with technologies enabling target tracking and/or micro-Doppler analysis. Therefore, Eve can enforce its deception by considering these advanced technologies. Bob can be forced to track the artificial target by updating (8) over multiple snapshots to follow Newtonian kinematics. As tracking filters are also based on kinematic equations, this ensures that the artificial target parameters match those used by the filters. In parallel, micro-Doppler signatures can be mimicked by either using empirical data or by simulating the appropriate pattern. For instance, human walking motion can be simulated through the Boulic model [36] by using Matlab's radar toolbox.

B. Invalidating the Surveillance Signal

As pointed out in (17), there are two options available to Eve for invalidating the surveillance signal. Before we discuss these options in detail, we point out that Eve can greatly benefit from estimating the distances¹⁰ shown in Fig. 1. To do so, Eve can use the round-trip time when Alice and Bob alternate their roles as Tx and Rx during the sensing negotiation stage, as explained in Appendix C.

1) *Preceding Jamming Signal*: If Eve can ensure the Case 1 signal alignment, then Bob will not perceive the surveillance signal. This corresponds to the best strategy for invalidating the surveillance signal. To successfully implement this strategy, Eve must accurately estimate the round-trip times (see in Appendix C) and the transmission schedule of Alice. By doing

¹⁰We remind that the topology parameters, e.g., the LOS distances, can be known before jamming without signal processing. Such information can be available if the attacker has access to the network topology, e.g., networks in public areas, or if the attacker can perform other types of measurements, e.g., distance measurement with laser meters. Having access to such information makes the attacker more effective for jamming. However, for the sake of brevity, our analysis will only focus on estimating these parameters with signal processing.

so, Eve can time its transmissions so that Bob receives only the jamming signal, and collects the predetermined amount of samples, thereby rendering the legitimate signal invisible.

2) *Forced Synchronization*: If the signals are aligned as in Case 2, Eve must force Bob to synchronize with itself instead of Alice. This forced-synchronization will lead to ICI on the surveillance signal where ridges replace the target peaks. There are two requirements to achieve this. First, the jamming signal power must be greater than the surveillance signal power at Bob. Second, the CFO on the jamming signal must be sufficiently high and different from the one on the surveillance signal. To satisfy the first requirement, Eve must know at least the distance between Alice and Bob, d_{ab} , and between itself and Bob, d_{eb} . Then, Eve can adjust its transmit power, forcing Bob to synchronize with itself¹¹. The second requirement will be achieved if Eve can estimate the CFO between itself and Alice $\eta^{(a)}$, and Bob $\eta^{(b)}$ during the sensing negotiation, and then compute $\hat{\eta} = \eta^{(b)} - \eta^{(a)}$. Now, Eve can artificially introduce CFO $\bar{\eta}$ that is much larger than $\hat{\eta}$, potentially with a different sign. Then, a corrupted surveillance signal becomes inevitable.

C. Qualitative Analysis

Now that various jamming strategies and different options to achieve them are discussed, they are qualitatively analyzed in Table III. (A1) Overcrowding Bob is the simplest approach since it has no additional requirements other than a single antenna. However, it introduces the artificial target along with the true ones. In case Bob can perform micro-Doppler analysis and/or target tracking, the true targets will still be identified. (A2) If only the artificial targets are desired at Bob, then multiple antennas are needed for beamforming to only use Eve's LOS with Bob and to avoid illuminating the real targets. This greatly increases the jamming effectiveness. However, it comes with increased complexity due to the AoA estimations and beamforming. (A3) Mimicking realistic target signatures is the most effective but complicated way to deceive Bob, especially when this is combined with A2. (B1) Preceding jamming signal dominance provides the best method to invalidate the surveillance signal since it will not be observed at all. However, it requires the estimation of the device distances, transmission schedules, and a timed transmission algorithm which will greatly increase the complexity. (B2) Forced synchronization is a reliable option if B1 is not available, since ridges replace the true target peaks. However, the presence of the ridges can still be detected by Bob, making it react accordingly. Moreover, Eve has to estimate the device distances to adjust its transmit power, and the relative CFO to create ICI.

V. NUMERICAL ANALYSES

In this section, we present comprehensive numerical results to examine the impact of a jammer on a WLAN sensing network.

¹¹Eve may want to avoid transmitting at the highest possible power to avoid power consumption, to be more stealthy and not detected by the neighboring cells, and to avoid saturating the analog front-end of Bob.

A. Simulation Parameters

The radar parameters and topology information can be found in Table IV. We use the Blackman window for sidelobe suppression along the range and speed dimensions. It is important to note that the RDMs shown here are not derived from the numerical solution of (7) or (16). Instead, they result from a full radar chain simulation, including channel propagation with convolution, time-frequency synchronization with correlation, and subsequent radar processing.

Fig. 4. Four RDMs are provided, corresponding to the surveillance, artificial, jammed with A1 and A2.

B. Results and Discussion

Target spoofing strategies A1 and A2 are studied first, where Eve is equipped with single and multiple antennas, respectively. Then combined strategies are evaluated. Finally, the probability of target detection is analyzed as a function of the artificial CFO.

1) *Injecting Artificial Targets*: In Fig. 4, the RDMs illustrate the WLAN sensing and artificial target injection concepts. The surveillance RDM depicts the physical channel between Alice and Bob, showing the synchronization peak $\langle 1 \rangle$ and the target $\langle 2 \rangle$. The artificial RDM, generated by Eve to be imposed on Bob, features the synchronization peak $\langle 3 \rangle$ and the artificial target $\langle 4 \rangle$. The bottom-left RDM shows what Bob perceives under the influence of A1 type of jamming. Here, the peak at zero range/zero-speed $\langle 5 \rangle$ corresponds to peak $\langle 3 \rangle$ in the artificial RDM, and the real target between Eve and Bob appears as peak $\langle 6 \rangle$. Although this target is located in a different range/speed cell compared to $\langle 2 \rangle$, it remains detectable by Bob. The artificial target peak $\langle 7 \rangle$ appears at its intended position, while the combination of the artificial and physical targets appears as another peak $\langle 8 \rangle$. In this particular case, Eve-LOS arrives earlier than Alice-LOS, causing Bob to time synchronize with Eve-LOS, which shifts the surveillance RDM along the range dimension. Hence, the surveillance RDM appears as the two peaks beyond 20 meters of range corresponding to the time difference of arrival between Eve's and Alice's signals at Bob. In other realizations, these peaks may appear beyond the limits of the CFAR detector. Hence,

TABLE III
DIFFERENT JAMMING STRATEGIES. REQUIREMENTS ARE DEFINED AS \mathcal{S} : SINGLE ANTENNA, \mathcal{M} : MULTIPLE ANTENNAS, \mathcal{P} : ADDITIONAL PROCESSING UNIT FOR TRACKING/MICRO-DOPPLER SIGNATURES, Θ : LOS AoAs, \mathcal{D} : LOS DISTANCES, \mathcal{T} : TIMED TRANSMISSION ALGORITHM, \mathcal{F} : CFO ESTIMATION.

Strategy	Requirement tags	Complexity	Effectiveness	Detectability by Bob	Target presence
Overcrowding (A1)	\mathcal{S}	Very low	Low	High	Artificial+True+Combined
Selective Target Injection (A2)	\mathcal{M}, Θ	Moderate	High	Moderate	Artificial+True
Advanced Target Mimicry (A3)	\mathcal{P}	High	Very High	Low	Artificial+True+Combined
Preceding Jamming Signal (B1)	$\mathcal{S}/\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{D}, \mathcal{T}$	High	Very High	Very Low	Artificial+Combined
Forced Synchronization (B2)	$\mathcal{S}/\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{D}, \mathcal{F}$	Moderate	High	Moderate	Artificial+Ridges

TABLE IV
SYSTEM AND TOPOLOGY PARAMETERS FOR NUMERICAL ANALYSIS, WHERE p_A, p_B, p_E , AND p_T CORRESPOND TO THE 2D COORDINATES OF ALICE, BOB, EVE AND THE TARGET, RESPECTIVELY. THE VELOCITY VECTOR AND RADAR CROSS-SECTION OF THE TARGET ARE INDICATED BY v_T AND σ_T , RESPECTIVELY.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Q	1024	p_A	(10m, 0m)
Q_{cp}	64	p_B	(0m, 0m)
B	80 MHz	p_E	(5m, 10m)
M	128	p_T	(5m, 10m)
M_o	100	v_T	(-3m/s, -3m/s)
f_c	5 GHz	σ_T	0.1m ²

Bob may discard these peaks without even considering them as potential echoes. The bottom-right RDM shows the effect of beamforming. Steering a null towards the real target makes it undetectable, and the only mobile peak that appears is the artificial target. In this particular realization, we also forced the Alice-LOS to arrive much later than Eve-LOS so that the surveillance RDM is not visible.

Fig. 5. Four RDMs for different strategy combinations.

2) *Combined Strategies*: In Fig. 5, four RDMs illustrate the combination of different jamming strategies. The top-left RDM shows the combination of overcrowding and preceding jamming. In this case, the true surveillance channel is not observable. However, the true and the combined targets are still present. The top-right RDM shows the combination of overcrowding and forced synchronization. Since Alice's and Eve's signals are somewhat aligned, the surveillance RDM is present. However, the peaks are replaced by the two ridges (1) and (2) due to the presence of ICI. This energy spreading does not occur in the speed domain since symbol-to-symbol phase shifts remain unaffected, thereby causing no degradation along

Fig. 6. Probability of detecting real and artificial targets as a function of CFO for two different subcarrier spacings: 312kHz for 802.11ac and earlier, 78kHz for 802.11ax and later. The OS-CFAR [37] algorithm is used for target detection, with 10^{-6} as the probability of false alarm. The real target speed is randomized over 5k realizations for each CFO value.

the speed dimension. However, the ridges are still Doppler-shifted due to the presence of the CFO. The bottom-left RDM, the combination of selective injection and preceding jamming, corresponds to the most effective jamming since only the artificial RDM is present, i.e., without additional targets or ridges. Finally, the bottom-right RDM corresponds to the combination of selective injection and forced synchronization. Similar to the top-left scenario, the peaks in the surveillance RDM are replaced by ridges. However, the additional targets are not present due to the use of beamforming.

3) *Target Detection Probability*: In Fig. 6, the impact of CFO on the probability of detecting (PD) the real and the artificial targets in the forced synchronization strategy is analyzed. The subcarrier spacing also varied between 78 kHz (802.11ax and later) and 312 kHz (802.11ac and earlier). For wider subcarrier spacing, when the CFO is below 3 ppm, the range IDFT still focuses most of the energy on a range cell, hence, the real target is detected. However, above 3 ppm, the PD of the real target dramatically decreases, meaning that most of the energy is spread along the range dimension, causing ridges. Narrower subcarrier spacing suffers much more from CFO. The critical CFO threshold at which a significant change occurs is roughly 1 ppm, and beyond this value, the PD rapidly decreases.

In parallel, the PD of detecting the artificial target does not depend on the subcarrier spacing or the CFO. This is expected since the CFO is present only on the surveillance signal but not the jamming signal. However, if the ridges caused by the CFO

and the artificial target are aligned along the speed dimension, the artificial target will not be detected. In such a case, Eve will unconsciously sabotage its target spoofing performance. This is why the PD of the artificial target is not 100% and varies for different CFO values: in some realizations, the artificial target is concealed by the ridges. This outcome cannot be avoided since the real target's speed (relative to the Alice-Bob channel) is unknown to Eve.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

In this section, we explore the design and implementation of an SDR-based jammer, specifically utilizing the USRP X310 platform.

A. Experimental Setup

Our experimental setup is similar to the topology provided in Fig. 1, except that the devices and the human target are inside a room as shown in Fig. 7. We use a metallic fan to emulate a mobile target due to the consistent speed pattern we get from the rotating blades, which helps diagnose RDMs. In our models and numerical analyses, we described the NDP/NDPA frames as if composed of a single type of OFDM symbol as a training field. However, these frames consist of multiple fields, such as legacy short and long training fields (L-STF and L-LTF) for coarse synchronization, and high-efficiency long training fields (HE-LTF) for fine synchronization [1]. For Bob to synchronize with Eve in a real WLAN sensing system, Eve must mimic these additional fields, including L-STF and L-LTF. However, we omit these fields in our models, simulations, and experiments since i) they are straightforward to implement; and ii) they are unnecessary for our purposes, as HE-LTF is the primary field for sensing processing.

The transmitted signals follow the structure shown in Fig. 8. Alice continuously transmits legitimate sensing signals, separated by $T_s = 1.32$ ms. In parallel, Eve transmits clusters of modulated OFDM symbols, with each cluster consisting of three identical OFDM symbols corresponding to the time instant m . This clustered transmission serves two purposes: i) ensuring signals for each time alignment case in (17), and ii) increasing the probability of at least one jamming signal aligning with the legitimate one. The jamming signal clusters are also separated by $T_s = 1.32$ ms, using the middle symbol of each cluster as a reference.

B. Results and Discussion

We show the experimental surveillance channels between Alice and Bob and Eve and Bob. Then we show the impact of the different combined strategies (A1-B1, A1-B2, A2-B1, and A2-B2), to relate to the simulation results in Section V.

1) *Surveillance Channel*: We present the RDMs for both the Alice-Bob and Eve-Bob channels, as shown in Fig. 9. In real-life wireless channels, static environmental features, like walls and furniture, produce multipath components (MPCs), manifesting as clutter peaks centered around zero-Doppler in both RDMs. We used a metallic fan to emulate a mobile target, resulting in four distinct peaks visible at approximately

Fig. 7. The picture of the experimental setup, consisting of a metallic fan as the mobile target and three USRP X310s: one to emulate Alice and Bob, and the remaining two to emulate Eve's array. For Eve's single antenna transmission: i) only the antenna at the far left is kept, and ii) the remaining antennas are removed to avoid coupling effects. For Eve's multiple antenna transmission: i) the AoA estimation stage is bypassed, instead, the angles are computed manually, and ii) the precoder matrix is designed to steer a null towards the target and a beam towards Bob as explained in Appendix B.

Fig. 8. Signal structure for jamming. Alice transmits the same OFDM symbol with PRI $T_s = 1.32$ ms, indicated with green. Meanwhile, Eve transmits in batches, each consisting of three identical OFDM symbols for time instant m , indicated with red.

3 meters and 6 meters in the bistatic ranges for the Alice-Bob and Eve-Bob pairs, respectively. These peaks correspond to the Doppler frequency shifts caused by the fan's blades. Additionally, there are target peaks associated with the fan that appear at farther ranges due to multipath effects, also known as ghost targets. Finally, the clutter and fan blade peaks exhibit unique characteristics in each RDM because of the differing bistatic geometries.

2) *Combined Strategies*: We present four RDMs in Fig. 10, each corresponding to different combined jamming strategies. These RDMs include an artificial target set at a 10-meter range and a speed of 5 m/s, marked with a red cross. The top-left RDM corresponds to the first strategy. Similar to the isolated RDMs in Fig. 9, the fan's signatures are visible as a set of peaks $\langle 1 \rangle$. The target peaks $\langle 2 \rangle$ result from the combination of the fan's signatures and the artificial target peak $\langle \times \rangle$. Moreover, since Eve transmits range/Doppler shifted signals for the artificial target, their interaction with the static environment also results in a range/Doppler shifted clutter $\langle 3 \rangle$ scaled by $\bar{\alpha}$. This can also be beneficial for more realistic deception. The top-right RDM illustrates the effect of forced synchronization, where the target peaks and clutter are replaced by ridges $\langle 4 \rangle$. Due to the CFO, these ridges shift along the speed dimension after folding multiple times. The bottom-left RDM demonstrates the most effective strategy, where Eve exploits the directivity of a linear array. However, despite this, the mobile target's signatures remain visible $\langle 5 \rangle$ due to the calibration errors and the array's sidelobes. Additionally, the

Fig. 9. The RDMs obtained for Alice-Bob and Eve-Bob channels while the mobile target is active. Black stars mark the peaks in Alice-Bob RDM for comparison.

clutter pattern differs from the top two RDMs because the scene is not isotropically illuminated. Finally, the bottom-right RDM represents the last strategy, characterized by the presence of ridges caused by the CFO.

3) Comparison of Numerical and Experimental Results:

We begin by discussing the similarities between the numerical analyses (Section V) and experimental validation (Section VI). In all cases, the artificial target is successfully introduced to Bob. The effects of different combined strategies align well with the numerical analysis. The simplest combination, A1+B1, shows numerous target peaks. Both A1+B2 and A2+B2 produce similar RDMs, dominated by ridges. The third strategy, A2+B1, generates the cleanest RDM, showing mainly the artificial target.

However, significant differences arise between numerical and experimental results due to real-world environments and hardware limitations. First, the static objects introduce clutter centered at zero-Doppler, along with ghost targets of mobile entities. Since the clutter pattern differs between Alice-Bob and Eve-Bob, Bob may detect these discrepancies and respond accordingly. Second, since Eve also transmits range/Doppler-shifted signals for the artificial target, the reflection of these signals from the static environment range/Doppler shifts the clutter peaks according to the artificial target. Third, the noise floor in experimental results is much higher than in simulations, which only account for thermal noise. Fourth, if the number of ridges, determined by the number of mobile target peaks in the Alice-Bob channel, is relatively high, the artificial target is more likely to be concealed by them. Lastly, when Eve uses A2 to steer a beam towards Bob and a null towards the target, the radiation pattern is imperfect due to calibration errors, making the mobile target peaks slightly visible.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper investigates the design and implementation of a target-spoofing deceptive jammer within a WLAN sensing framework, highlighting the vulnerabilities of OFDM-based JCAS systems to various jamming strategies. We offer a

Fig. 10. The jammed RDMs with combined strategies, with $\eta_w = 5\text{ppm}$. The black stars correspond to the range/Doppler cells of the true target, while the red cross corresponds to the (10m,5m/s) cell for the artificial target.

comprehensive quantitative and qualitative analysis of how techniques such as overcrowding, selective target injection, and forced synchronization can manipulate RDMs in WLAN sensing, leading to significant disruptions in target detection and tracking. Our experimental validation confirms the feasibility of these jamming strategies using cost-effective and easily deployable SDR platforms, demonstrating that even without sophisticated hardware, a jammer can effectively compromise the integrity of the sensing process.

Our findings identify the most vulnerable aspects of WLAN sensing as: i) standardized OFDM symbols, ii) joint time and frequency synchronization, and iii) unprotected over-the-air negotiation. These results highlight the need to address such vulnerabilities in the design of future WLAN sensing and JCAS systems, particularly as these technologies become increasingly integrated into critical applications.

In conclusion, this study underscores the significant risks posed by target-spoofing deceptive jamming in wireless sensing environments and lays the groundwork for developing more robust countermeasures against such threats. Future research should focus on securing physical-layer waveforms, refining synchronization and detection algorithms, and exploring adaptive techniques to mitigate the impact of spoofing and jamming on OFDM-based JCAS systems.

APPENDIX A

JOINT TIME AND FREQUENCY SYNCHRONIZATION

Bob uses the signal received through the LOS path in a bistatic configuration for joint time and frequency synchronization. Let's assume that the LOS signal is dominant, meaning $\alpha_0 \gg \alpha_p, \forall p$ and that the propagation delay of the LOS path satisfies $\tau_0 < \tau_p, \forall p$. We can express the received LOS signal sampled at time $t = nT + mT_s$ (where n and m denote the fast and slow time indices, respectively) as follows [38]

$$r[n, m] = \alpha_0 s[n - n_0, m] e^{j2\pi\eta(nT + mT_s)} \quad (18)$$

where we omit the noise, η represents the CFO between Alice and Bob, and $s[n, m]$ is the transmitted signal. To

perform coarse synchronization, Bob computes the lag-1 auto-correlation over a sliding window of the received samples. The auto-correlation at lag k is given by

$$\Xi[k] = \sum_{n=-Q_{cp}}^Q r[n+k, m]r^*[n+k, m+1]. \quad (19)$$

After substituting the received signal into the equation, the strongest peak in the auto-correlation output occurs at $k = n_0$ corresponding to the arrival time of the LOS path since $\alpha_0 \gg \alpha_p, \forall p$. Assuming that the transmitted signal is normalized to $\sum_{n=-Q_{cp}}^Q s[n, m] = 1$, the complex amplitude of this peak is defined as

$$\Xi[n_0] = |\alpha_0|^2 e^{-j2\pi\eta T_s} \quad (20)$$

where the phase of $\Xi[n_0]$ is directly related to the CFO between Alice and Bob. Hence, Bob can synchronize to the timing of the LOS based on the peak at $k = n_0$, and estimate and compensate the CFO using the phase of the peak $\hat{\eta} = \angle \Xi[n_0] / 2\pi T_s$. This process ensures that Bob is correctly synchronized in both time and frequency domains, using the dominant LOS signal as a reference.

APPENDIX B PRECODER MATRIX

This precoding matrix must satisfy the following constraints

$$\mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{a}(\hat{\theta}^{(a)}) = \mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{a}(\hat{\theta}_0) = 0 \text{ and } \mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{a}(\hat{\theta}^{(b)}) = 1. \quad (21)$$

where $\mathbf{a}(\theta) = [1 \ e^{j\pi \sin(\theta)} \ \dots \ e^{j\pi(N-1) \sin(\theta)}]^T, \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is the array response vector with N elements, and the antennas are separated by half wavelength. Then, the precoding vector is defined as $\mathbf{w} = (\mathbf{I}_N - \mathbf{P}_A) \mathbf{a}(\hat{\theta}^{(b)})$, where $\mathbf{I}_N \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ is the identity matrix, and $\mathbf{I}_N - \mathbf{P}_A$ is the matrix that projects $\mathbf{a}(\hat{\theta}^{(b)})$ onto the null space of $\mathbf{A} = [\mathbf{a}(\hat{\theta}^{(a)}) \ \mathbf{a}(\hat{\theta})], \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 2}$ [39], where $\mathbf{P}_A = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{A}^H$.

APPENDIX C ROUND-TRIP-TIME FOR DISTANCE ESTIMATION

Here, we explain the RTT-based distance estimation for two networks. The first is the legitimate WLAN sensing network, where both Alice and Bob estimate $\tau_{ab} = d_{ab}/c$ for themselves. The second one is the eavesdropping network, where Eve estimates $\tau_{be} = d_{be}/c$, $\tau_{ae} = d_{ae}/c$ and $\tau_{ab} = d_{ab}/c$ where c is the speed of light. We assume that RTT-based distance estimation takes place after CFO compensation. The first RTT is summarized as follows [40]:

- 1) Alice transmits and starts its reference clock.
- 2) Bob receives the signal and starts its reference clock.
- 3) Bob waits for the standardized duration of τ_x , then transmits.
- 4) Alice receives the signal after $2\tau_{ab} + \tau_x$ seconds, then estimates τ_{ab} .
- 5) Alice waits τ_x seconds, then transmits.
- 6) Bob receives the signal after $3\tau_{ab} + 2\tau_x$ seconds, and estimates τ_{ab} .
- 7) Both devices now have τ_{ab} .

The second RTT is summarized as follows [41]:

- 1) Alice transmits.

- 2) Eve receives the signal and knows that Alice has transmitted. Eve does not start its reference clock yet and waits for the next transmission.
- 3) Bob waits τ_x seconds, then transmits.
- 4) Eve receives Bob's signal and starts its reference clock since it knows that $\tau_{ab} + \tau_x + \tau_{be}$ seconds have passed.
- 5) Eve listens for the next transmissions and keeps measurement times as C_1 to C_4 .

Once all the reception times are collected, the propagation delays are calculated as

$$\tau_{abx} = \frac{C_3 - C_1}{2}, \quad \tau_{be} = \frac{3C_1 - C_3}{2}, \quad \tau_{ae} = C_2 - C_3 + C_1 \quad (22)$$

where $\tau_{abx} = \tau_{ab} + \tau_x$.

Fig. 11. RTT-based distance estimation procedure. Green and red arrows correspond to the propagation delays over the related distances. Blue lines correspond to the standardized idle time τ_x .

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